

Peculiar Electron- May Possible

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Abstract

In this note a new idea is proposed, the idea is to predict possible a new particle as same as electron but not Fermionic in nature.

Standard model undoubtedly states that every matter in the universe is made up of two kinds of particles electrons and quarks. Both are fermions and obeys exclusion principle. In this note we will present two things one a formula to compute electron's e/m ratio using the concept of de Broglie wavelength, and second the primary task is to speculate the particle same as electron (here same means same charge, same mass) but of different spin thus stating that of different statistics. Our prediction can be stated as follows- Our second fundamental thought is a general prediction that a particle must exist similar to electron in nature like electrostatic charge (-1), behavior and may be mass but must possess a spin of $\frac{1}{4}$ therefore this electron like first generation new particle is not Fermionic in nature but it seems that it is elementary, if only electron is elementary. The e/m of this predicted particle is probably and approximately equivalent to that of an electron if its mass is nearly same as electron. This new particle must have its own antiparticle like positron with all properties of positron excluding spin so spin is $\pm \frac{1}{4}$. The movement in magnetic field of these new particles and its antiparticle is same as electron and positron respectively. An electron neutrino like particle should also exist (as its partner) which must be chargeless but posses a spin of $+-1/4$ and may be it is a Majorana like particles but not fermions. One needs to confirm these ideas in super weird physical laboratories. However the formula to compute electron's e/m using Broglie wavelength parameter is

$$Beh - F_B \lambda m = 0$$

Therefore the ratio is

$$\frac{e}{m} = \frac{F_B \lambda}{Bh}$$

where F_b is the force experienced by and electron in magnetic field, λ is wavelength, B is the magnetic field and h is the Planck's constant